

Notes

Studies on Diphenyl Lead(IV) Diiodide Complexes of Substituted Thioureas

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THE organolead(IV) compounds are of considerable interest as wood preservatives, anticorrosive paints, pesticides and fungicides, as revealed in recent reviews^{1,2}. The preparation and spectral studies on organolead(IV) complexes of dithiocarbamates³, phosphinoides⁴, triazoles⁵ have been reported. Bosco and Cefalu⁶ have shown that planar tridentate ligands with ONO and SNO donor atoms form 1 : 1 monomeric species with a quasi-tetragonal bipyramidal geometry around lead(IV). Later, octahedral complexes of diorganolead(IV) with QNNO tetradentate ligands have been studied by DiBianca *et al.*⁷. A survey of literature shows that no reports are made on complexation behaviour of diorganolead(IV) towards substituted thioureas. In the present communication synthesis and properties of diphenyl lead(IV) diiodide complexes with substituted thioureas have been described.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. grade. The ligands were prepared according to the published procedures employing freshly purified anilines^{8,9}. The diphenyl lead(IV) diiodide was prepared by the method described in the literature¹⁰.

Ditododiphenylbis(phenylthiourea)lead(IV): Phenylthiourea (0.31 g, 0.002 mol) in dry methanol (50 ml) was refluxed with diphenyl lead(IV) diiodide (0.61 g, 0.001 mol) for about 2 h. The methanolic solution was concentrated to small volume (20 ml). After cooling, the orange coloured complex separated out was filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum. A similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of other complexes of diphenyl lead(IV) diiodide with the ligands, *viz.* *o*-tolylthiourea (*o*-totu), *o*-methoxyphenylthiourea (*o*-MeO.ptu), *o*-hydroxyphenylthiourea (*o*-HO.ptu), diphenylthiourea (dptu), ethylenethiourea (entu) and *o*-phenylenethiourea (*o*-phentu). In some cases, addition of 2-3 drops of water to the hot solution facilitated the crystallisation of the complex.

The complexes were analysed for metal, nitrogen, sulphur, carbon, hydrogen and iodine. The data are presented in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements were taken on a Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge. Infrared absorption spectra (4000-650 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 instrument using KBr pellet. Far-infrared spectra (650-200 cm^{-1}) were taken on a Beckman IR-12 instrument. The uv-visible spectra (700-200 nm) were recorded in 1,4-dioxane solution on a Beckman-25 instrument.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data and some physical properties are reported in Table 1. The crystalline orange coloured complexes obtained have the $\text{PbPh}_2\text{L}_2\text{I}_2$ stoichiometry (L=substituted thioureas). The molar conductance values 7-12 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, in 1,4-dioxane solution account for non-electrolytic nature of all the complexes.

Thiourea and its derivatives can coordinate to the central metal ion through sulphur or/and nitrogen. The metal-sulphur bonding has been established in Co^{II} ^{11,12}, Ni^{II} ¹³, Cr^{III} ¹⁴, $\text{U}(\text{VI})\text{O}_4$ ¹⁵, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ¹⁶ complexes of substituted thioureas. However, metal-nitrogen bonding is observed in Sn^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Cu^{I} and Pt^{II} complexes¹⁷. It is significant to note that Hg^{II} coordinates through both the sulphur and nitrogen of ethylenethiourea molecule¹⁸. This makes it interesting to ascertain the coordination of substituted thioureas to lead(IV).

The assignment for various bands have been made according to the convention made by Jensen and Nielsen¹⁹. The ν_{NH} band in the region 3400-3150 cm^{-1} undergoes a slight blue-shift (30-60 cm^{-1}) except in phenylthiourea and *o*-tolylthiourea complexes. In general, these bands are broader than those of free ligands and a negative shift in some complexes clearly suggest the presence of intense N—H...S intermolecular hydrogen bonding which is also apparent from the blue-shift for δ_{NH_2} in the region 1620-1590 cm^{-1} compared to free ligand^{14,20}. The positive shift (10-25 cm^{-1}) of $\nu_{\text{asy}} \text{NCN}$ band in the region 1530-1480 cm^{-1} in case of complexes indicate the increased double bond character of C—N bond and a small positive shift (5-15 cm^{-1}) for composite ($\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{NCN} + \delta_{\text{NH}_2} + \nu_{\text{OS}}$) around 1380 cm^{-1} clearly shows sulphur coordination of the ligand to the metal. The bands observed in the region 775-750 and 730-660 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{OS} with a slight contribution of ν_{ON} and ν_{OS} , respectively. The red-shift (10-40 cm^{-1}) with the reduction in intensity of these bands is a clear indication of the sulphur coordination to central metal ion. The far-infrared spectral data provide further evidence for

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND UV-VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA OF LEAD(IV) COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						Absorption maxima	
			Pb	C	H	N	S	I	λ_{max} kK	ϵ_{max} $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
PbPh ₂ (ptu) ₂ I ₂	220-21	9.72	22.26 (22.55)	34.06 (33.95)	2.65 (2.83)	6.15 (6.09)	6.64 (6.97)	28.62 (28.50)	37.84 22.22	10740 1463
PbPh ₂ (o-totu) ₂ I ₂	270-72	10.12	21.65 (21.89)	35.06 (35.47)	2.92 (3.17)	5.64 (5.92)	6.83 (6.76)	26.92 (27.23)	38.58 21.98	16560 1598
PbPh ₂ (o-MeO.ptu) ₂ I ₂	230-32	12.25	21.38 (21.15)	34.62 (34.31)	2.84 (3.06)	5.63 (5.72)	6.48 (6.53)	26.21 (26.33)	37.03 22.22	15950 1633
PbPh ₂ (HO.ptu) ₂ I ₂	225-26	10.47	21.56 (21.79)	32.56 (32.80)	2.86 (2.73)	5.68 (5.89)	6.52 (6.73)	26.94 (27.11)	37.58 22.22	11040 1760
PbPh ₂ (dptu) ₂ I ₂	157-58	7.62	19.42 (19.35)	41.83 (42.58)	3.28 (3.17)	5.18 (5.23)	5.62 (5.97)	23.82 (24.07)	35.58 22.22	5082 267
PbPh ₂ (entu) ₂ I ₂	143-45	9.16	25.19 (25.36)	26.24 (26.43)	2.47 (2.69)	6.71 (6.82)	7.62 (7.83)	31.23 (31.56)	37.03 21.98	25000 2854
PbPh ₂ (o-phentu) ₂ I ₂	166-68	9.95	22.38 (22.65)	33.83 (34.10)	2.63 (2.40)	6.45 (6.12)	6.64 (6.95)	27.98 (28.18)	34.36 22.32	6310 632

sulphur bonding^{11,12}. A medium-strong band in the region 290-270 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibration. The metal iodine stretching frequency was not observed as it absorbs below 200 cm^{-1} .

The electronic spectra of ligands and their complexes were studied in 1,4-dioxane solution and absorption maxima observed in case of complexes are presented in Table 1. The ultraviolet spectra of the ligands exhibit intense absorption maxima at 40-37 kK (ϵ 16000-8000) and a less intense band around 34 kK (ϵ 6000-1000). The higher energy band is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition while lower energy band is assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of thiocarbonyl group of the ligand molecule. These transitions are very well compared with the thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition at 254 nm and thiocarbonyl $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition at 291 nm of the thiourea molecule in diethylether. In complexes these transitions were not shifted to appreciable extent but only broad and more intense band is observed in the range 37-34 kK (ϵ 25000-5000). A new band is observed around 22 kK (ϵ 3000-250) in all the complexes. This band may be due to the ligand metal charge transfer which clearly implies that a stable complex has been formed.

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Study of Pseudo Aromatic Behaviour and Stereochemistry of 4-(Ethyl)imino-pentane-2-one Complexes of IV Main Group Elements

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CONSIDERABLE work has been reported on the aromatic behaviour of coordinatively saturated, neutral and monomeric metal acetylacetonates¹⁻³. These complexes form molecular complexes by the donation of electron density from the chelate ring to the iodine molecule. However, no attempt seems to have been made to extend these studies to similar complexes of Schiff bases. With this in view, the dielectric and refractometric techniques have been employed for determining the formation and stoichiometry of the molecular complexes of metal Schiff base derivatives with iodine. From the experimental data, the geometry of the resulting complexes has also been inferred.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were dried by the usual methods^{3,4}.